

NH₂) and 9.9 (1H, s, NH)(D₂O exchangeable); *m/z* 118 (*M*⁺ 13.7%), 87 (4.0%), 76 (30.8%), 75 (75.0%), 70 (2.8%) and 59 (7.8%). The compound was identified as aliphatic acid (as methyl ester, 2, lit.⁹ m.p. 208°d as methyl ester).

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Extractive AAS Determination of Lead

SANTI RANI DAN (BISWAS) and ARABINDA K. DAS*

Chemistry Department, University of Burdwan,
Burdwan-713 104

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THE present paper describes a method for selective and quantitative extraction of trace quantities of lead by the liquid chelating exchanger (LCE), trifluoroacetylacetone type (RCOCH₂COCF₃) in the presence of 1,10-phenanthroline (phen.) using chloroform as diluent and its subsequent determination by flame atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AAS). The method has been successfully applied to determine lead content in alloy containing phosphorus.

Experimental

LCE (RCOCH₂COCF₃; R=C₉H₁₉) from Versatic-10 was prepared following the procedure described earlier^{1,2}. A 0.1 *M* solution of LCE in ethanol was used in the present work. A stock solution of lead(II) was prepared by dissolving Pb(CH₃COO)₂·3H₂O (Sarabhai Merck) in double-distilled water and was standardised complexometrically³. All the other reagents used were of AnalaR grade.

Absorbance measurements were made with a Shimadzu 646 atomic absorption spectrophotometer maintaining the following conditions: lead hollow cathode lamp current, 7 mA; burner height, 5 mm; wavelength, 217.0 nm; slit width, 1.9 Å; air flow rate, 10 dm³ min⁻¹; acetylene flow rate, 2.6 dm³ min⁻¹; optimum working range, 5–20 ppm. The pH values were measured with a Sambros 335 digital pH meter.

Procedure: To a solution of lead (100 mg dm⁻³) in a 50 ml separatory funnel, dilute ammonia was added to adjust the pH to ~7.0, tris-buffer solution (2 ml; pH=7.2) was then added and the total volume of the solution was made up to 10 ml. To it each of the 0.1 *M* chelating exchanger (1 ml) and 0.03 *M* phen. were added and the mixture was shaken. Then chloroform (5 ml) was added, shaken and allowed to settle for 5 min. The organic phase was taken into another separatory funnel and the aqueous phase was washed with chloroform (2×2 ml) and taken in the same separatory funnel. The resulting solution was stripped back into 0.1 *N* HNO₃. The aqueous phase was taken and volume was made up to 10 ml. The absorbance value of the resulting solution was measured on the AAS and the amount of lead was found out from the calibration curve.

The method was applied for the determination of lead in different alloy samples obtained from the Bureau of Analysed Samples (Table 1).

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF LEAD IN ALLOY^a SAMPLES

Description of alloy constituent (%)	Lead ^b found	
	Direct AAS	Present method
Gun metal (6 g): Cu (86.4), Zn (1.3), Sn (10.5), Pb (1.02)	1.015 ±0.010	1.019 ±0.014
H.T. Brass (10 g): Cu (60.8), Zn (32.0), Fe (1.56), Al (3.34), Mn (1.36), Pb (0.23)	0.229 ±0.003	0.231 ±0.002
Phosphor bronze (7 g): Cu (88.4), Sn (10.1), P (1.31), Pb (0.02)	c	0.021 ±0.0002

^aFrom Bureau of Analysed Samples Ltd., Middlesbrough, Cleveland, U.S.A., August 1975. ^bAverage of three determinations. ^cCan not be determined.

Results and Discussion

Lead was quantitatively extracted from aqueous medium in the pH range 6.6–9.0. Quantitative extraction of lead was achieved with chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, tributyl phosphate and benzene; the percentage of extraction being 100 in each solvent. Other solvents, viz., 1,2-dichloroethane (90.0%), cyclohexane (56.7%) and methyl isobutyl ketone (46.7%) were also used. Concentration of LCE varied from 0.075 to 0.600 *M* in chloroform, 0.1 *M* LCE solution was sufficient, and the excess amount did not affect the extraction of lead. Extraction was increased with increasing phen.

concentration and was complete at 0.03 *M* of the reagent. Lead was completely stripped back from chloroform layer into HNO₃ of different strengths (0.1–2.0 *N*). Hence, a 0.1 *N* HNO₃ solution was used as the stripping agent. Extraction was complete within 1 min, and 30 s was enough for back-extraction. To be on the safe side, 5 min was allowed to settle the equilibrium in both the cases.

Separation of lead from various ions : Lead was separated from binary, ternary and quaternary mixtures of known amounts of various ions (amount in parenthesis in μg); the results for the determination of 20 μg lead (within an error of $\pm 2\%$) are as follows: (i) binary mixtures: Na^I, K^I, Li^I (2000); Ca^{II}, Ba^{II}, Sr^{II} (800); Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Mn^{II} (250); Mg^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} (200); Cu^{II}, Al^{III}, Ga^{III}, Cr^{III} (160); Ti^{IV}, VO₃⁻, MoO₄²⁻ (100); Fe^{II} (60); large amounts of F⁻, NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻, PO₄³⁻ did not interfere; (ii) ternary and quaternary mixtures: (a) Ba^{II} (500) + Mn^{II} (200); (b) Ni^{II} (100) + Zn^{II} (100); (c) Al^{III} (100) + Cu^{II} (100); (d) Mg^{II} (100) + MoO₄²⁻ (50) + Fe^{II} (50); (e) Ca^{II} (500) + Cd^{II} (200) + VO₃⁻ (50); (f) Sr^{II} (500) + Cr^{III} (100) + Ti^{IV} (50).

Nature of the extracted species : To determine the composition of the extracted species extractions were carried out by keeping the concentration of lead constant and varying pH of the medium. The data were found to satisfy the linear relation⁴,

$$\log D = \log K_{\text{ex}} + (m+n) \log [\text{H(LCE)}]_0 + n\text{pH}$$

where, *D* = distribution ratio, *K_{ex}* = extraction constant, *m* = number of adduct molecule, *n* = number of chelating agent bound to metal and [H(LCE)]₀ = concentration of chelating agent in the organic layer, which gave *n* = 2.0, *m* = 1.0. Hence the stoichiometry of the extracted complex should be Pb(LCE)₃ (phen.). A similar β -diketo complex of lead has been reported earlier⁶.

Phosphor bronze which contains 1.31% phosphorus in the matrix, demands separation of lead before estimation by AAS. In lead determination by AAS, H₃PO₄ and PO₄³⁻ always cause interference and involves a lengthy separational procedure⁶. The present method is very simple and rapid in this respect. Nevertheless, gun metal and H.T. brass showed same results with or without separation.

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Extraction of Copper by Liquid Chelating Exchanger followed by its AAS Determination

SHUVENDU S. BHATTACHARYYA

and

ARABINDA K. DAS*

Department of Chemistry, University of Burdwan,
Burdwan-713 104

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THE present communication reports the use of a β -diketo liquid chelating exchanger¹, RCOCH₂-COCH₃ (LCE) for extraction of copper and its determination by AAS. The method has been applied for the determination of copper in human blood samples.

Experimental

Absorbance measurements were made with a Shimadzu 646 atomic absorption spectrophotometer. pH values were measured with a Sambros 335 digital pH meter. CuSO₄·5H₂O (E. Merck, G.R.) was used for the preparation of stock copper(II) solution.

Liquid chelating exchanger : Versatic-10 (C₁₀-isomeric monocarboxylic acid, Shell Chemical Co., London) was distilled and the exchanger was prepared in two steps. Versatic-10 was mixed with large excess of absolute ethanol and a little concentrated H₂SO₄, and the mixture was refluxed for 24 h. Ethyl ester thus produced was separated and purified by distillation. The resulting ester was then condensed with large excess of pure acetone in presence of sodium ethoxide by refluxing the mixture for 24 h. The resulting liquid β -diketo compound was separated and purified.

Procedure : To an aliquot (1.0 ml) of Cu^{II} solution containing 50 μg of the metal, dilute ammonia solution was added to adjust the pH to 8.0 and the mixture was transferred to a 50 ml separatory funnel. The tris-buffer (2 ml; pH 8.0) and 2.2×10^{-4} *M* LCE in chloroform (10 ml) was added to it and the mixture was shaken and allowed to settle. The organic layer was separated and any trace of organic phase associated with the aqueous layer was washed with chloroform (2 × 5 ml) and mixed with the organic layer. The organic layer was then stripped with 0.05 *M* HCl (5 ml), and the